

Measuring the Protective Value of Simulated Dragon Hides against a Thrust from a Simulated Unicorn Horn

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Abstract

To determine if the Household of Malone & Mallet would align with the Dragons or the Unicorns; an experiment was devised and executed to determine if a unicorn might be able to pierce the hide of a dragon with its horn. The method used a Oryx horn, that was then driven at a target of 152.4mm x 152.4mm x 76.2mm certified 10% ballistics gel¹ at a speed of 2000mm/second to a depth of 50.8mm. Force from the blow was measured at the base of the horn by 4 balanced load cells at a rate of 2000 readings per second. Three materials were chosen to simulate dragon hide based loosely on three historical references. The results were surprising in that the Unicorn was able to pierce all three materials, however, the strongest material (alligator hide) did push they system past its measuring limits.

In the end, the family choose to align with the Unicorns; as the horn was successful in penetrating all three hides.

Introduction

As a family, we could not come to a decision for Braggart's War III if we should align with the Dragons or the Unicorns. It was determined that we would align with Unicorns if, during experimentation, we found that a unicorn horn could penetrate a dragon hide. This determination would be made using technology in development for an experiment to evaluate the relative protective value of different forms of late 16th century civilian clothing.

There is already a body of research regarding stabbing with knives². Members of the SCA have attempted to ask similar questions as well with unpublished research³. While that body of research does include analysis of the profile of a sharp point in a controlled system⁴, and the force profile over time using an instrumented knife blade⁵; the current body of research does not provide direct insight into whether or not a Unicorn could successfully stab a Dragon.

¹ Clear Ballistics Gel used was certified by the vendor to meet FBI 10% ballistic gel specifications.

² Knight, "The Dynamics of Stab Wounds"; Jones, Nokes, and Leadbeatter, "The Mechanics of Stab Wounding"; Nolan, Hainsworth, and Rutty, "Forces Generated in Stabbing Attacks."

³ Zakes, "The Machine - Moondragon."

⁴ Hainsworth, Delaney, and Rutty, "How Sharp Is Sharp?"

⁵ Jones, Nokes, and Leadbeatter, "The Mechanics of Stab Wounding."

Methods

Figure 1

The Testing System

An apparatus (figure 1) was developed that would drive a stabbing implement at a target under power through the entire movement. The machine uses a mechanical design like a single axis of a CNC mill⁶ with a pair of linear guide rails mounted to a frame with a ball screw. A saddle with linear guides and a ball screw nut are mounted to the guides & ball screw. Linear motion of the saddle is achieved by the turning of the ball screw. The sensor and horn were then mounted to the saddle.

For this experiment the speed of the motion and the accuracy of the movement were key. As such the ball screw picked is one that moves the saddle 40mm with a single rotation. This was then driven by gear increase of 3:1. A single rotation of the drive motor then rotates the ball screw 3 times for a total movement of 120mm per rotation of the drive motor.

To accurately manage the movement; a 500 watt closed loop servo that produced 7.4 N-m of torque at 1500 RPM⁷ was chosen. Motion control was handled via custom developed software running on a Raspberry Pi 3b.

Measurement of the forces were obtained via 4 load cells each balanced to +1mv of output at no load. The Sensor platform with the 4 load cells were then calibrated to accurately read 500 grams (+/-20 grams) at 2000 readings per second. The horn was then attached to this sensor by passing bolt through the sensor and tightening it down.

⁶ "CNC Milling Machine Axis Explained [Complete DIY Guide] - CNCCookbook: Be A Better CNC'er."

⁷ "CPM-SDHP-3436P-ELN | Shaft Diameter = 0.5000in | Not Including Shaft Seal | Teknic."

Figure 2

The Unicorn Horn

Picking a proper simulation of a unicorn horn started by validating that according to period sources; the horn is in fact a horn and not an antler or tusk. Tusks like those of a narwhal or a elephant are in fact teeth⁸ anatomically speaking, other than the narwhal we were not able to find historical depictions of unicorns where in the horn was associated with the mouth. The next point of analysis for the picking of a simulation was validating that the horn was in fact a horn and not an antler. Antlers and Horns are anatomically very different; the latter being made of bone and solid, while the former is made of keratin and continually grows and wear⁹.

Claudius Aelianus (175 – c. 235 AD) wrote *“India produces horses with one horn, they say, and the same country fosters asses with a single horn. And from these horns they make drinking-vessels, and if anyone puts a deadly poison in them and a man drinks, the plot will do him no harm. For it seems that the horn both of the horse and of the ass is an antidote to the poison.”* In his work *De Natura Animalium*¹⁰.

From this ancient detail we know the horn is not an antler as it is hollow and can be drunk from, combined with images like *The Unicorn in Captivity* tapestry (figure 2)¹¹, the determination was made to find a horn, not an antler, that is long and straight. The Oryx has such a horn, and so a horn was sourced from the UK and imported.

Dragon Hides

Three types of materials were tested to be our dragon hide simulation. The first was that of a crocodile or alligator, as Marco Polo describes his dragons in chapter 49¹², The second was that of a stingray based on Isaiah 27:1 *“In that day the LORD with his sore and great and strong sword shall punish leviathan the piercing serpent, even leviathan that crooked serpent; and he shall slay the dragon that is in the sea.”*¹³. Lastly, because we have no evidence that dragons are in fact real, a modern fictional dragon analog was picked, snakeskin was used to simulate that of smaller dragons like swamp dragons from *Discworld*¹⁴ and other pseudo dragons from modern fiction.

⁸ “Elephant Tusks - Elephant Facts and Information.”

⁹ HEIMBUCH, “Antlers or Horns? What’s the Difference?”

¹⁰ Scholfield, *On the Characteristics of Animals*.

¹¹ “The Unicorn in Captivity (from the Unicorn Tapestries) | South Netherlandish | The Met.”

¹² Polo and Rugoff, *The Travels of Marco Polo*.

¹³ *Holy Bible*.

¹⁴ Pratchett, *Guards! Guards!*

As far as our research can determine both the unicorn and the dragon are entirely mythological creatures and as such these simulations will provide reasonable analogs to a fictional conflict.

Running of the Experiment

The execution of the experiment was done in the following process:

- 1) The thrust motion was executed at full speed without a target three times to define a baseline of motion experienced by the load sensors
- 2) The target of ballistics gel was mounted and placed in the target path such that the horn would stab at least 50.8mm deep
- 3) The thrust motion was executed three times against ballistics gel with no dragon hide to define the control for the experiment
- 4) For each dragon hide simulation: the hide was soaked for 30 minutes, then drip dried, then tap dried. Then at least three thrusts were executed against different parts of the hide such that no strike was closer than 1" from a previous strike.
- 5) The results of each run were serialized into a CSV file and the depth of the penetration into the ballistics gel was measured from the surface of the gel with the hide removed using bamboo skewer.

Results

Control – No Target

Figure 3

The three runs with no target show an initial acceleration force of 11792g, 9470g, 10556g consecutively (Figure 3), these numbers will be useful to validate that the sensor is consistent during the other runs.

This kind of correlation of data was seen through each run, so for the remainder of the results, each run will be shown in its own chart.

Control – Ballistics Gel Target

Figure 4

The peak force of the thrust was 13,600 grams, and the chart (Figure 4) deviates from the control no target in that there continues to be positive force on the horn during deceleration as it continues to stab into the ballistics gel.

Figure 5

Run 2 (Figure 5) shows a slightly higher peak force at 14,119 grams of force

Figure 6

Run 3 (Figure 6) targets more towards the corner of the ballistics gel and showed a higher force of 19,100 grams of force. There are multiple possible confounds to the additional force measurement, it is possible that the others were this high, but the sample missed the measurement, the target location (the corner) provided additional resilience, or even natural variation in the material.

Run	Peak Force
1	13,600g
2	14,119g
3	19,100g
Average	15,606g

Experiment 1 – Snakeskin (fictional dragon from modern literature)

Figure 7

Figure 8

The first run of the snakeskin (Figure 8) shows a small boost in protective value at 17,849 grams of peek force

Figure 9

Snakeskin run 2 (Figure 9) continues the trend of protection over the control with a measurement of 18,602 grams at the peak of the impact.

Figure 10

Run 3 (Figure 10) of the snakeskin was extraordinarily anomalous with a peak strike force of only 6,851 grams, and the cause was unknown. We did also measure that strike 3 was the deepest penetration of the horn into the ballistics gel (see below). As such a 4th test was run.

Figure 11

Run 4 (Figure 11) of the snakeskin showed a result that was more in line with the other runs at 14,315 grams of force. However, it is lower than the first two. At this point hypothesis were being suggested that the material was breaking down as the material was punctured more and more.

Depth of penetration was also measured for this experiment (Figure 12)

Figure 12

Run	Peak Force	Penetration depth
1	17,849g	40.30mm
2	18,602g	43.65mm
3	6,851g	48.24mm
4	14,315g	37.54mm
Average	14,404g	42.43mm

Note: Without the third run the average is higher than the control at 16,922 grams of peak force and a penetration of 40.49mm

Experiment 2 – Stingray (Sea Dragon/Biblical reference)

Figure 13

Figure 14

Run 1 (Figure 14) of the Stingray shows a significant increase in the protective value of the stingray's distinctive skin with a peak force of 33,953 grams of force. We also see a large growing force over several milliseconds rather than the near instantaneous peak as we saw in the control and the snakeskin.

Figure 15

This run (Figure 15) again shows the ramping force but a slightly lower peak of 27,836 grams.

Figure 16

Figure 16 shows run 3 on the stingray skin. We continued to see the degradation in performance over time as the peak force was 24,116 grams. Of note there was a 4th hole made in the stingray between run 2 and 3 due to operator error during the targeting process.

Figure 17

Figure 17 shows the penetration of the horn during the stingray skin tests. Interestingly these are very consistent depths.

Run	Peak Force	Penetration depth
1	33,953g	36.72mm
2	27,836g	38.36mm
3	24,116g	34.62mm
Average	28,635g	36.57mm

Experiment 3 – Alligator (Marco Polo’s Dragon)

Figure 18

Figure 19

The first Alligator run (Figure 19) was to the softer part of the hide and was still required significant force at 38,418 grams at its peak. Like stingray there was a slow buildup of force taking multiple milliseconds before it hit the peak force.

Figure 20

Run 2 (Figure 20) of the alligator was run against a thicker part of the hide, while penetration was successful, we find that the force required was greater than our machine can currently measure (49,000 grams) and peaked for a number of microseconds.

Figure 21

The final run of the day (Figure 21) was of the thickest part of the alligator skin and again the run peaked our sensor. It also peaked it sooner and for longer. The result of this run was that the target fixture was knocked out of alignment by this test. Despite those issues, the horn did penetrate the alligator hide.

Figure 22

Penetration of the alligator hide behaved as expected and decreased with increasing thicknesses of the hide.

Run	Peak Force	Penetration depth
1	38,418g	24.08mm
2	49,000+g	14.94mm
3	49,000+g	9.31mm+
Average	N/A ¹⁵	16.11mm ¹⁶

¹⁵ Due to peak force being greater than the sensor an average of force is not available

¹⁶ Because the target fixture was knocked out of alignment by the forces during the last run, this number is not accurate.

Discussion

Sensors and Data Acquisition

The data is acquired via the reading of 4 differential¹⁷ load cells that each use a wheatstone bridge¹⁸ strain gage configuration. The signal is then amplified by a single ended instrument amplifier¹⁹ before being processed by an analog to digital converter²⁰. The analog to digital converter is then read by the machine software via i2c using SPI. This system produced results that were calibrated to +/- 20 grams.

However, there is significant room for improvement due to design issues uncovered during the development of the project. First off, the load cells used were harvested from consumer grade kitchen scales due to issues discovered during assembly, testing and time constraints. The corrective action for this is to order and use calibrated commercial load cells. Next, because load cells are differential in the signal they produce, but our instrument amplifier could only read from 0v and up ½ of the range of the load cells was lost. This may have contributed to the issue we saw with the data in experiment 3. The resolution for this issue is to use a different instrument amplifier so the full range of the load cell can be used. This should have limited up stream impacts as our Analog to Digital converter handles differential signals.

Lastly, we worked to limit noise in sensor by using a separate 5v power supply just for the load cells and instrument amplifier. However, there was still significant noise. Given the constraints in sampling data at such a high data rate more effort needs to be taken, in the form of analog filters and higher quality power supplies, to reduce the noise of the signal being sent to the Analog to Digital Converter.

Motion

The motion was obtained through the use of a closed loop servo that was capable of a peak torque of 7.4 N-m at 1500 RPM. The servo drove a 60-tooth gear that engages a 20 tooth gear that drives a 20 mm ball screw. The ball screw has a sweep of 40mm so for each rotation of the ball screw the machine moves the horn and sensors 40mm. Because a single rotation of the servo leads to 3 rotations of the ball screw, this provides a system capable of a top linear speed of 3000mm/second. However, the ball screw has an effective length less than 800 mm so reaching 3000mm/s is not likely a possible motion path without a mechanical crash.

During testing we did observe some highspeed retraction motion during the end of the thrust. It is our believe this may be coming from the servo not being able to decelerate in time and over shooting its target then correcting. More analysis on that behavior is needed to determine if it will have an impact on future experiments.

The servo is also capable of communicating its torque load during testing, this may provide a second data point (at 400hrz) to correlate with our load cell force data. Investigations into using the real time torque output data should be considered as a potential improvement.

¹⁷ Differential load cells send signal data from -3mv to positive 3mv based on flex of the load cell.

¹⁸ "Wheatstone Bridge for Strain Gauges."

¹⁹ INA 125P Texas Instruments Instrument Amplifier which can handle 0 to 36 volts but does not natively handle differential signals was used with a gain of 604 set by a 100 ohm resistor.

²⁰ ADS 1256 Analog to Digital converter was used at a sample rate of 2000 samples per second and a gain of 1.

Orchestration and Motion Control

The machine movement and data capture is handled by a Raspberry Pi 3b running Raspian Stretch as its operating system. The computer is outfit with a touch screen to make operation of the tests quick and easy. Custom software using C, C++ and Python was written with each language used where appropriate.

The foundation of the software is an open source C Library²¹ to communicate with the various connected devices. Built on top of that was custom multi-threaded C++ drivers to both send timed signals to the servo and read incoming data from the analog to digital converter. Finally, a touch enabled UI responsible for planning movements and serializing incoming data to CSV files was built in Python. The entire application was open sourced and made available at <https://github.com/jhandel/swordbot>

One of the limitations of the current application architecture is the lack of a real time operating system. Because the actions we are doing are measured in millionths of a second the delays caused by a normal distribution of Linux can cause issues. Digital data noise, over shooting movements by the servo, even slightly inaccurate speeds could all be caused by inaccurate timing at these kinds of time scales. As such research should be done into rebuilding the Linux kernel to support real time access to the hardware and then the software updated to work with accurate timing.

Lastly the C++ drivers should be updated so that the timing of the servo is in sync with the timing of the data capture. In this way specific points in the motion (like the point of planned impact) can be marked in the data making analysis easier and more accurate.

Frame and Mechanical Components

The frame of the machine was built using t-slot aluminum rails which are common for tasks similar to this. The aluminum t-slot rails are easy to cut to length and constructed into a frame via brackets, screws and bolts. Along with the t-slot, 15mm linear rails and matching guides were used to provide a secure parallel path for the sensor to move on. While off the shelf components like the T-Slot, Liner Rails, screws, nuts and brackets make up much of the machine; 7 custom aluminum components were fabricated in house using a 3 axis CNC mill.

Given how the machine moves the addition of angled legs may make for a more stable platform for testing in the future, but otherwise the frame and mechanical components worked well.

Cad drawings of the machine can be downloaded at <https://a360.co/2JLcLN7>

Target, Target Fixture, and Ballistics Gel

The Target was made from 19mm plywood built into a 152.4mm square that was 82.5mm deep. This was then attached to a solid frame made of 13mm plywood. A second 13mm plywood frame was then used to sandwich the target material and press it to the ballistics gel. The fixture to hold the target was made of the same t-slot aluminum framing material as the machine. The target was mounted to two

²¹ "Bcm2835: C Library for Broadcom BCM 2835 as Used in Raspberry Pi."

aluminum uprights via t-slot nuts and bolts. Lastly the Ballistics Gel used is certified to behave to the same specification as the FBI uses known as 10% ballistics gel²²

The target worked well, and we were able to quickly change test materials and replace the ballistics gel blocks. However, the fixture did become misaligned during the running of experiment 3 and will need to be reinforced before future testing is done. Also, a process of melting down and reusing the ballistics gel needs to be developed to quickly switch out our ballistics gel blocks. With the right process in place we should be able to decrease the reuse of a single block of gel from 6 tests down to 4. This will likely lead to an increase in the quality of the results.

Proof of Concept Findings

It is important to reframe the above discussion and even the results of these experiments with the goal of this series of tests. This system is ultimately to be used to run very specific tests regarding stabbing forces involved in penetrating various analogs to late 16th century clothing. To that end the primary concerns for this set of experiments is consistency, repeatability and reliability.

Seeing that the force data was in line with expectations was a success. Secondly seeing that multiple runs under the same conditions returned consistent results validated our concerns around repeatability. Lastly running tests up to the toughness of alligator hide showed the resilient and reliability of the machine and technology under stress.

This set of experiments also provided an opportunity to develop processes for validating data, and a general structure for the reporting scientific findings.

²² Nicholas and Welsch, "Institute for Non-Lethal Defense Technologies Report."

Conclusion

In all cases the simulated unicorn horn was able to successfully pierce all the dragon hides without accounting for the strength and mass of an actual unicorn. As expected, the thinner skin provided little protection and the alligator simulation was in fact quite strong. Of note during the experiment the unicorn horn simulation showed no signs of wear when penetrating these various protective skins. We had originally thought that perhaps the stingray skin would cause some visible wear with its hard plates, but the horn pierced the skin with no visible stress. The data also supports that should a dragon be covered in a homogeneous surface like that of the snake or stingray, multiple wounds decreases the protective value of the unpierced skin near a wound.

Given that the horn was driven to the same depth in every test, the wound should have been to the same depth, however when measuring the depth of the penetrations, it was found that the thickness of the hide decreased the depth of the penetration. So thicker hides not only increase the force necessary to pierce the skin; they also decrease the penetration into the ballistics gel at a given depth.

It is our conclusion that in addition to unmeasurable magical interventions the unicorn does have an effective direct offensive with its horn and could injure a dragon. While it is true a dragon has its own list of physical and mythological attacks, findings regarding those attributes will have to be run separately as they were outside the scope of this set of experiments.

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